

R&D collaboration networks in robotics: A geographical perspective using worldwide co-patent data

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Abstract. The purpose of this study is to identify R&D hot spots and characterize the structure and dynamics of global R&D collaboration networks in robotics from a geographical perspective. We use patents as marker for R&D activities, and accordingly focus on technologically oriented R&D. In its empirical strategy, the study draws on information on patents applied for between 2002 and 2016. We employ a search strategy to identify relevant robotics patents based on detailed levels of the Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC). One of the most innovating elements is the assignment of all patents to more than 900 global urban areas based on the inventor addresses given in the patents and their geocoding. The co-patent networks are examined from a Social Network Analysis (SNA) perspective by means of robotics co-patents also observed for the time period 2002 to 2016, giving rising to a global network where urban areas are the nodes inter-linked by joint inventive activities recorded in robotics patents. Global SNA measures illustrate structures and dynamics of the network as a whole, while local measures indicate the specific positioning and roles of urban areas in the network. The results highlight most prominent urban hot spots in terms of specializing in robotics R&D, pointing to the increasing role of emerging economies, in particular China. The global robotics R&D has grown immense both in total patenting, but also in terms of R&D collaboration activities between urban areas. Also for the networks, growth is not equally distributed, but is characterized by significant spatial shifts, both in terms of cities declining or climbing up the specialization ranking, but even more in terms of the spatial network structure.

Keywords

R&D networks, R&D collaboration, R&D internationalization, Co-patents, robotics, Globalization, Social Network Analysis

1 Introduction

Today it is widely documented in the literature, that new knowledge created by Research and Development (R&D) activities is the basis for successful innovation (see, e.g., Howells 2000), and that the creation of new knowledge is increasingly accomplished within a complex web of interaction between researching organisation, often referred to as R&D collaboration networks (see Scherngell 2021 for a recent overview). Looking at knowledge creation processes and underlying network structures from an economic geography perspective, most importantly the *geography of innovation* literature stresses the spatially localised nature of knowledge creation, hypothesized to be one of the main explaining factors for divergent spatial economic development (Audretsch and Feldman 1996). Against this background, we can observe over the last two decades an enormous growth of empirical studies investigating the geography of knowledge creation, R&D activities, networks and innovation, related to new upcoming datasets intending to capture different types of knowledge and R&D outputs.

However, most of these works tend to look at knowledge creation and R&D collaboration from an aggregated perspective, in particular in terms of different underlying knowledge domains or technological fields (Wanzenböck et al. 2019). Therefore, recently interest in tracing the geography of knowledge creation and R&D collaboration networks for specific relevant technological fields has grown tremendously, e.g. against the background of the revitalized debate on mission-oriented research policies (Mazzucato 2018). In the latter context, the focus does not lie on classical economic sectors or technologies, but on cross-cutting fields that are of specific relevance for addressing important societal challenges, such as climate change, health, or ageing societies.

In this study, we intend to contribute to this new focus on specifically relevant technological fields by shifting attention to geographical dynamics of R&D activities and related collaboration networks in the field of *robotics*. Clearly, robotics is not only considered as important contributing field to the growth of the world economy related to remarkably increasing demand (Shukla and Shukla 2012), but in some major aspects may directly responds to some of these societal challenges such as demographic ageing or environmental threats. On top of that, robotics is even considered to comprise the ability for structurally transforming economies as a whole, and therefore become pivotal for regions and countries for economic competitiveness, since improved capabilities of robots and the benefits derived from the implementation in the production cycle accelerate the demand across many industries, causing significant growth potentials and productivity gains. Related to the rising importance of robotics, more intensive collaborations in R&D have also become more frequent in recent years. The robotic industry is generally a highly research and capital intensive technological segment that requires a lot of expertise and knowledge (WIPO, 2016). However, although the robotic environment is expanding and becoming more relevant, only few studies exist that systematically trace the global landscape of robotic innovations and the related global R&D collaboration networks behind it (Keisner et al. 2015).

Against this background, the overall objective of this study is to identify and empirically characterise the changing global R&D landscape in robotics from a geographical perspective. First, we want to identify global R&D hotspots specialised in robotics R&D at a detailed geographical level of urban areas, and, second, we intend to trace for the first time global robotics R&D collaboration networks, illustrating the dynamics within the network on a global scale from the perspective of urban areas as most important places of innovation. We use patents as marker for R&D activities and accordingly focus on technologically oriented R&D with a clear goal of economic commercialisations, rather than basic, fundamentally scientific oriented R&D. Specifically patent-based indicators are extremely useful for comparing and monitoring trends in the technological output (Dachs & Pyka, 2010), but also in the context of tracing R&D collaboration by means of co-inventions, i.e. patents featuring inventors located in different urban areas or countries.

In its empirical strategy, the study draws on information on patents applied for between 2002 and 2016. We employ a search strategy to identify relevant robotics patents based on detailed levels of the Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC). However, one of the most innovating elements of this study is the assignment of all patents to more than 900 global urban areas based on the inventor addresses given in the patents and their geocoding. To identify R&D hotspots and global specialisation patterns, we calculate a Revealed Technological Advantage (RTA) index measuring the level of the urban area's relative technological specialisation in the robotic segment. The R&D collaboration networks are examined, following previous research (see e.g. Hu et al. 2015) from a Social Network Analysis (SNA) perspective by means of robotics co-patents also observed for the time period 2002 to 2016, giving rising to a global network where urban areas are the nodes inter-linked by joint inventive activities recorded in robotics patents. Global SNA measures illustrate structures and dynamics of the network as a whole (e.g. size of the network, intensity of collaborations, etc.), while local measures indicate the specific positioning and roles of urban areas in the network.

The remainder of the study is organised as follows. *Section 2* clarifies the relevant theoretical and conceptual foundations of R&D and related collaboration networks in the context of robotics as important breakthrough innovation. *Section 3* is devoted to the methodological approach for analysing the global R&D landscape in robotics, introducing in some more detail the empirical setting, including the patent data used, the study area, the time frame, as well as the analytical approaches in form of the RTA and the SNA analysis. The empirical results of the study are discussed and presented in *Section 4*, starting with an illustration of the findings of the RTA analysis in terms of global R&D robotics hot spots, followed in *Section 5* by a discussion global robotics network structures and dynamics based on the SNA including illustrative network visualisations at the level of global urban areas. *Section 6* concludes the study by summarising and reflecting on the most essential results and findings and finalises with possible research gaps and future research ideas.

2 Robotics as breakthrough innovation and the role of R&D collaborations

In this study we follow previous research (see, e.g., Atkinson, 2019) and delimit *robotics* as a segment of automation *technologies* replacing human efforts. This involves all kind physical machines or devices programmed to perform a variety of different tasks, with some level of interaction with the environment, but limited or no input from a human operator¹. In recent years, the global economic but also societal demand for robotics has been increasing remarkably (Küpper, et al., 2019). The market for industrial robots has been growing significantly at rates in double-digit numbers per annum after millennium (see, e.g. Shukla and Shukla 2012). Recently, industrial robots operating in factories around the world reached a record number of 2.7 million in 2019 (mainly applied in handling and assembling in automotive, food and plastic industries) which is an increase of 12% compared to 2018 (IFR, 2020)². Main drivers of this growing demand are robots' improved capabilities, their widespread potential use, productive activity and falling costs (Oxford Economics, 2019). In addition, manufacturing processes are getting more complex as the number of customised and diversified products rises, making robots highly attractive for increasing efficiency and flexibility (Küpper, et al., 2019). In the latter context, the fast development of artificial intelligence technologies – e.g. used for patterns recognition or automatised communication – integrated in robotics applications strongly contribute to the increasing decision-making capabilities (WIPO, 2015, Gomes & Pereira, 2019), and accordingly their attractiveness of robots, mainly in the manufacturing sector but also in service industries (Van Roy, et al., 2019).

Despite the recent growth, investments in robotics are expected to increase further across all industries, especially in the automotive, electronics and pharma, but also with an enormous potential to disrupt existing economic and social facets of everyday life, considering robotics technologies as one of the most important breakthrough innovation nowadays (Keisner et al. 2015). In this context, two inter-related factors are specifically important illuminating the robotics sector: *First*, robotics is a highly research-intensive, dynamic, and complex technological segment (WIPO, 2016), requiring particular expertise, knowledge endowments and specialisations as the products in the robotic market are ranging from classical industrial robots to fully autonomous service robots. In reference to the findings of He et al (2009), this directs per se to an increasing demand for collaborations among specialised robotic

¹ According to the International Federation of Robotics (IFR) and in line with the international standard ISO 8373, robots can be, based on their intended application, classified into industrial and service robots (IFR, 2021). Industrial robots are defined as an “automatically controlled, reprogrammable multipurpose manipulator programmable in three or more axes”, which can be placed in a predetermined location or flexible in relocation. Service robots can “perform useful tasks for human or equipment excluding industrial automation applications”, either by acting partially autonomous (with human interaction) or fully autonomous (without human robot intervention). Another approach classifies robots into fixed (or industrial) and mobile robots, depending on their mechanism of interaction and working environment (i.e. well-defined or uncertain environments) (Ben-Ari & Mondada, 2018). Historically, fixed industrial robots were the first robots that were implemented in manufacturing processes, performing tasks such as welding, painting, moulding plastics and palletizing, while working separately to humans (IFR, 2018). Moreover, the IFR (2021) defines the class of robots that carry out tasks in collaboration with workers in industrial settings as collaborative (industrial) robots, also sometimes referred to as *cobots*.

² In terms of use, almost half of the worldwide distributed industrial robots were applied for handling in 2019. Around 20% of the industrial robots were employed in the welding area and nearly 10% in the assembling area (Statista, 2019). In the same year, the automotive industry installed with 105,000 units globally the most industrial robots (mainly for increasing production flexibility), followed by the electronics (mainly for quality assurance) and metal industry. In both food and plastic and chemical products industry were over 10,000 units of new industrial robots installed (Statista, 2019).

companies, given the diversified pieces of knowledge (e.g. motive power, control system, sensing) to be integrated in the R&D and innovation process (WIPO 2016). *Second*, given the high R&D intensity on the one hand, in combination with the growing demand and economic potentials on the other hand, robotics technologies are to a substantial degree subject to public R&D funding initiatives across a number of countries worldwide, but also for supra-national organisations such as the European Union (EU). IFR (2020) shows that most countries invest in robotics; China for example is seeking to achieve a major breakthrough for key components and tries to enhance robots' integration with new-generation information technology while having a budget of 577 million dollars (2019). Japan planned to invest 351 million dollars (2019) in R&D projects and focuses for instance on the development of medical and supporting devices for the aging population. Finally, the EU's key target is to digitalise the industry with the application of robotics technologies.

Such public programmes come into play as they are considered as substantial drivers for innovations, for competition in the industry and for economic productivity growth in general (see e.g. Scherngell et al. 2020; He et al. 2009). Moreover, public R&D programmes recently tend to fund not single actors, but joint consortia in dedicated R&D projects, with the aim to sustain knowledge circulation in the regional or national system of innovation. These R&D collaborations can be viewed as a dynamic network whose structure develops and deepens over time. Related to this, increasing technological complexity and challenges derived from globalisation, such as higher competition and a fast-changing environment, accelerate the need for international cross-border R&D collaborations (Goetze, 2010). Three main arguments are stressed in this context: *First*, expertise and knowledge are shared and transferred into the R&D project by the collaboration partners. Taking Schumpeter's perspective, the combination of external knowledge creates new knowledge among researchers that increases the quality and output of R&D in the collaboration network (Schumpeter, 1934). *Second*, the increasing complexity and challenges in the innovation process make it almost impossible to be specialised in every segment – an issue of particular relevance for the case of robotics based on the characterisation of the field put forward above. Collaborations among R&D actors are needed to pool and share resources, such as knowledge, machines, and equipment. *Third*, researchers can take advantage of the network that is created or already exists among the organisations. They learn and accumulate new knowledge from constantly shared and reviewed knowledge and information in the network (Asheim et al. 2007).

The empirical investigation of the study at hand as a whole is inspired and designed against the background of these theoretical and conceptual considerations. Given the comprehension of robotics as a breakthrough innovation, due its high R&D intensity and growth potential, on the one hand, and the strong interest of policies at different levels, on the other hand, a systematic characterisation of the global robotics R&D landscape is of great interest, in particular since spatially detailed insights are scarce in literature so far. We hypothesize that the global R&D network in robotics has grown over the past decades, but that it is also highly dynamic in terms of new actors, and accordingly geographical locations

come into play. In what follows we illustrate our empirical setting and the detail out the methodological approach, before we present an empirical characterisation of the global robotics R&D landscape from the perspective of hotspots and R&D collaboration networks.

3 Data and methods

The empirical strategy employed in this study follows a large body of previous empirical works using international patent applications for empirically tracing R&D activities and collaboration networks (see, e.g., Lata et al. 2015, Breschi and Lenzi 2016, Hazir et al. 2018, Scherngell et al. 2020, among many others). Patents grant a property right securing the patent holder a return on R&D investments (WIPO, 2015), and is one the most widely used indicators in innovation research as marker for new knowledge as outcome of R&D activities with a commercial application perspective (Archibugi and Planta 1996, OECD 2001). In our empirical approach, we mobilize the location of inventor addresses given on patent documents for tracing R&D hotspots, on the one hand, and inter-regional co-inventive activities, referred to as co-patents, for tracing R&D collaboration networks, on the other hand. Co-patents are defined as patent documents featuring at least two different inventors in two different regions (here urban areas), giving rise to an inter-regional R&D collaboration activity for the patent under consideration. Note that in using co-patenting, we trace a very specific form of commercially oriented, technological collaborative R&D, in contrast to other indicators such as co-publications or joint projects that are more indicative of scientific collaborations. In the robotics context, patents seem to be specifically suitable as robust indicator on new relevant knowledge because the field is highly research-intensive which requires intensive capital expenditures and R&D often takes place several years before commercialisation. (Keisner et al. 2015, Bonadio et al. 2018).

Patent data in study is traced from the RISIS Patent database (spring 2020 edition), available from the RISIS research infrastructure³. One of its most interesting features in context of our research focus is the very detailed geocoding of inventor addresses to functional urban and rural areas worldwide⁴. The unit of observation of the RISIS patent database are priority patents, the very first patent application worldwide to protect the respective invention. Moreover, it has standardized information on patent applicants by employing semi-automated cleaning of applicant names, mainly companies (see for details Laurens and Laredo 2019, on the construction of the database). Based on Keisner et al. (2015) we

³ RISIS Patent is available via the RISIS research infrastructure (risis2.eu) and derived from the EPO PATSTAT database. RISIS patent is specifically relevant for tracing geographical dynamics of knowledge creation. In RISIS Patent, an address is identified for 75% of inventors (to be compared with 10% in the initial raw EPO PATSTAT data) and 67.4% of the addresses are geocoded and associated to ‘functional areas’ (urban and rural) worldwide, mobilizing the RISIS CORTEXT geocoding service. The share of geocoded addresses varies according to the countries. It exceeds 80% in most of the western countries (Laurens, Villard, & Ospina Delgado, 2020).

⁴ Note that we use the term urban areas in this study, though also rural areas are included in the data, but patents are almost exclusively recorded to urban areas. However, there are a few rural areas appearing in terms of robotics patents which is marked by the addition ‘.rural’ to a specific area.

employ a patent mapping strategy that uses 13 CPC classes⁵ to extract the patent data from the RISIS patent database (see Table A1 in the Appendix for a list of the CPC and a respective description of the technological content). Data have been extracted for the first priority years from 2002 on and were grouped into three different time periods: (1) 2002-2006, (2) 2007-2011, and (3) 2012-2016 for the longitudinal analysis. In total, the sample dataset includes 47,936, with 41,397 of them assigned to an urban area.

In our methodological approach, we use the patent data to identify global R&D hot spots and specialisation patterns in robotics. Regional specialisation in robotics exists when a spatial uses a comparatively high proportion of its inventive capacities for their development (Möller, 2020), measured by the Revealed Technological Advantage (RTA) index (OECD, 2013) defined as

$$RTA_{ik} = \frac{P_{ik}}{\sum_{i=1}^n P_{ik}} : \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m P_{ik}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m P_{ik}} \quad (1)$$

where p denotes the number of patent applications, i the urban area ($i=1, \dots, n$) and k the technology class robotics (being the sum of the CPC codes listed in Table A1). Accordingly, the RTA index is the ratio of the regional share of patenting in robotics divided by its regional share of total patenting in all sectors (Vertova, 1999). The index is equal to one when the share of robotics exactly to the share of robotics patenting worldwide; smaller than one indicates an under proportional share of robotics, greater than one indicates an over proportional share and thus a specialisation in robotics in that spatial unit (OECD, 2013). To avoid the well-known small number problem for RTA analyses (see, e.g., Pintar and Scherngell 2021) ensure a meaningful comparison between urban areas, the data set was reduced to urban areas that show a total patent count greater than 2,000 (see Appendix Table A3 and A4). Furthermore, spatial units that had a robotic patent count of zero were removed from the data set.

Turning from R&D hotspots and specialization patterns to R&D network collaboration, we employ – following recent related works a Social Network Analysis (SNA) perspective to characterize their structure and dynamics. In general, SNA has come into fairly wide use for the analysis of social systems, been to be interpreted at the individual level of socially interacting individuals, but also come increasingly to analyze internationalization trends in networks of R&D collaboration across regions or countries (see, e.g., Scherngell et al. 2021, Hu et al. 2015). This is usually done by aggregating individual level information (in our case inventors) on collaborations to the regional level and shifting attention – away from the traditional variable-centric approach – to a structural-relational angle.

⁵ CPC is an abbreviation of “Cooperative Patent Classification”, which is an extension of the International Patent Classification (IPC) system. CPC is an internationally recognized patent classification system and hence a fitting reference point for classifications and searching patent applications in robotics. Its unified system is organized in a hierarchical way. More precisely, the technology fields are separated into nine sections (A-H and Y) with approximately 250.000 subdivisions (European Patent Office, n.d.).

In our analytical approach, we initially need to formally define the network under consideration. Graph theory sets out the basic mathematical framework to formally describe our global R&D collaboration network. In our case, we define a graph $G = (N, L, V)$ with $N = \{N_1, N_2, \dots, N_g\}$ being a set of nodes (here urban areas) which is related through a set of edges $L = \{L_1, L_2, \dots, L_M\}$ and a set of weights $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_M\}$ for each edge, in this study the number of co-patents between two urban areas. The topology of a graph can be decoded in a n -by- n adjacency matrix:

$$X_t(i, j) = \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \cdots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \cdots & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{n1} & x_{n2} & \cdots & x_{nn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where one element of X corresponds to the number of joint co-patents between urban areas i and j at time t . The total number of neighbors i.e. partner countries of a node is referred to as degree of this node. With the adjacency matrix as defined by equation (1), we can derive a number of relevant global (describing the network structure as a whole) and local (describing the role and positioning of individual nodes) network analytical measures. The following global network measures are used (for a formal derivation see Wasserman and Faust 1996, or Hu et al. 2015 in a similar context):

- The *average degree* is defined as the sum of the nodes' individual degrees divided by the total number of nodes in the network. The indicator is used to identify the connectedness in the network. The higher the average degree, the better the integration of the actors in the network.
- The *density* is the ratio between the number of edges and the highest possible number of edges. A value of 1 suggests that all nodes are connected with each other and a value of 0 suggests that none of the actors are connected with each other.
- The *average path length* is defined as the on average shortest path between all pair of nodes. A path is a sequence of different edges and nodes that connects two nodes with each other, and its length is determined by the edges the path contains. The average path length is an important indicator for the connectedness and cohesion of the network as well as for the knowledge exchange within a network. The lower the coefficient, the higher and more efficient the knowledge flow.
- *Clustering* is an indicator that describes the number of "cliques" in a graph, i.e. strong connected sub-graphs and localised knowledge pools. The more cliquish a network, the higher the clustering coefficient. If the underlying network has a small average path length and a high clustering coefficient, the network can be characterised as a small world network.
- In the case of *degree centralisation*, the actors' individual centralities (described below for the local measures) are used to describe the centralisation of the entire network or in other words the concentration of the graph. There are two extremes: (a) star-like network with a value of 1 and (b) fully connected graph with a value of 0. In a star-like network, one actor has the most central position in the network while the other peripheral actors have no or little connections between each other. This central actor is often characterised as a technological gatekeeper who enforces

innovative processes and the communication flow significantly. The opposite of a star-like network is a fully connected graph where all actors are connected with each other.

As local measures for identifying the local positioning of individual urban areas, we use three measures pointing to different roles of the different urban areas in the network:

- The degree-based centrality is defined as the number of direct connections that a single node has to other actors in the collaboration network. A high amount of connections indicates that a single actor holds an influential position and is better integrated into the network than actors.
- The betweenness centrality of a single node is calculated by the sum of the total number of shortest paths between two nodes divided by the sum of the number of those paths that pass through the node. Actors that show a high betweenness are able to contribute global knowledge into the network and have considerable control and power over the information flow. These actors are particularly important in a network as they bridge actors or groups that otherwise would be disconnected.
- The eigenvector centrality is defined as the extent and quality of connections that links a node to other nodes that are prominent in the network. The term peripheral node describes an actor who has only few connections and the term hub describes an actor that has many connections. Since actors with high eigenvector centrality (i.e. hub) are well connected to influential and central actors, they enjoy high prestige. Therefore, the term prestige centrality is often used as a synonym when describing an actor who has well established and precious connections.

All SNA indicators – both global and local – have been calculated using R and the igraph package (<https://www.r-project.org/>). For visualisation purposes, the open-software Gephi was used which helps to display large graphs and reveals patterns and trends in the network. More specifically, the Fruchterman-Reingold Algorithm, which is a force-directed layout algorithm, was used to display the network whereby the node size corresponds to the weighted degree centrality of a node, and the thickness of the lines corresponds with the number of co-patents between them.

4 R&D hotspots and specialization patterns

This section shifts attention to the empirical results of the study, initially reflecting on an illustration and interpretation of the R&D hotspots and specialisation based on the RTA measures as defined in the previous section by Equation (1). Table 1 presents the top ten R&D hotspots and most specialised urban areas in robotics R&D worldwide for the period 2012-2016. The RTA indices (most right column) are put into perspective against the total number of patents for the earliest (2002-2006) and the latest (2012-2016) time period under consideration, and a growth rate between the two periods. Overall, the empirical results remarkably confirm the enormous general growth trend of robotics R&D over the past two decades. Actually, we can observe a quite substantial increase in robotic patenting activity as growth rates mostly show values above 100%. Note that this is the case for all of the 160 urban areas included

in the RTA analysis (see Table A4 in the Appendix for an overview on all RTA indices for each urban area included).

Turning to the R&D hotspots, the RTA values indicate that the top ten areas have considerable specialization advantages. The values range from 8.83 to 20.09, indicating that there are some areas in a country that excessively focus on robotic R&D activities, and that these spatial concentration tendencies have become even more pronounced in the recent past.

Table 1. RTA analysis of top ten areas

Area	Patents robotics 2002-2006	Patents robotics 2012-2016	Growth rate in % (02/06 - 12/16)	RTA 2012-2016
Ann Arbor	34.28	99.60	190.59%	20.09
Stockholm	13.80	190.76	1282.33%	19.05
Detroit	147.90	325.54	120.11%	17.57
Aichi rural	132.27	399.18	201.80%	14.38
Kitakyushu	7.12	88.40	1142.19%	13.35
Stuttgart	232.00	384.84	65.88%	13.17
Karlsruhe	16.72	49.35	195.18%	11.32
Goeteborg	51.92	75.86	46.12%	11.28
Munich	75.76	229.88	203.42%	10.40
Frankfurt am Main	14.96	68.31	356.62%	8.83

Notes: Area abbreviations are provided in the Appendix (Table A2); Calculations include only areas that have a total patent count greater than 2,000

Some findings in terms of the top R&D hotspots identified are particularly interesting:

- Ann Arbor (US) has highest RTA index while having one of the lowest robotic patent counts, i.e. it is a highly specialized area in robotics dedicating the majority of its resources in robotic R&D activities. Clearly, there is strongly relation to its geographical proximity to Detroit, one of the traditional global robotics hot spots.
- Stockholm (in Sweden) and Kitakyushu (in Japan) show, with growth rates above the thousand percentage mark, by far the strongest development in robotic patenting. In combination with a high RTA index, these two urban areas shifted their focus to robotic R&D activities and expended their specialization advantage considerably more recently.
- Among the top ten, we find regions from the US, Germany, Japan and Sweden. German and US regions have lower growth in comparison to Stockholm and Kitakyushu, being already very active in robotic patenting. Still, they are above average specialized urban areas in robotics R&D.

To get a better understanding of the activities and driving forces of the specialization advantages in the top ten RTA areas, Table A5 in the Appendix shows the top three actors (i.e. companies, research institutions or universities) who are the most active and present in robotic patenting between 2012 and

2016 in the top ten areas. In general, companies in the automotive industry are the most dominant patent applicants in robotics, for instance, Ford Global Technologies, GM Global Technology Operations, Daimler, and Toyota. While most urban areas show a strong specialization in the automotive industry, Stockholm and Kitakyushu, that have also the highest growth rates in terms of patent activity between the first and second period, interestingly show different industry orientations. In Stockholm, two of the top three companies (Aktiebolaget Electrolux and Husqvarna) operate in the household, and agriculture and forestry industry. The area Kitakyushu is with Yaskawa Denki – as the most active patent applicant – highly specialized in the production and distribution of industrial robots. Furthermore, it is the only top ten RTA area where a research organization (National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology) is among the top three robotic applicants. Overall, it is striking that research facilities (i.e. universities or public research organizations) are not very active in robotic patenting in the top ten RTA areas. However, areas in Asia – especially Beijing, Shanghai, Guangzhou, and Seoul – have a comparatively high share of research facilities operating in robotic patenting, pointing to a more publicly followed strategy to promote robotics R&D.

Figure 1. Dynamics of RTA Rankings

Figure 1 provides additional information on the developments and movements of specialization advantages on the area level. It correlates the RTA rank of areas from the second period (2007-2011) to the RTA rank of areas from the third period (2012-2016), depicting movements of ascending (above the line) and descending (below the line) urban areas between the considered periods. Labeled areas are those who have won more than 60 ranks, and those who lost more than 28 ranks. The rank correlation of specialization advantages between 2007-2011 and 2012-2016 is 0.82 and the average rank change is 12.08, indicating that there are on average more urban ascending areas than descending ones. Overall, the large range of the diagram designates that there is a high dynamic in the RTA index movements.

While some regions stayed relatively close to their position in previous periods, some expectations are noteworthy. First, there are five Chinese urban areas strongly ascending, showing the highest development in robotic specialization developments. Second, there is a shift from national hotspots to other areas in the US. For instance, Indianapolis, Houston, and Minneapolis lost more than thirty ranks, while Pittsburgh, San Francisco, and Baltimore won more than sixty ranks. Third, some areas and their movements are particularly striking. Tel Aviv's RTA index increased from 0.056 in 2007-2011 to 0.935 in 2012-2016 (see Appendix Table A4), which is an immense growth and shows again how important robotic technology has become in recent years. In contrast, Moscow's RTA index decreased from 0.286 in 2007-2011 to 0.037 in 2012-2016 (see Appendix Table A4).

5 Dynamics of global robotics R&D collaboration networks

While the identification of global R&D hot spots in robotics for the first time at the level of urban areas is interesting, R&D activities are – as discussed from a theoretical perspective in Section 2 – nowadays widely accomplished within a web of interacting actors, increasingly located in different regions, or even countries (see, e.g. Scherngell et al 2020 for the case of global ICT networks). Accordingly, this section puts emphasis on discussing structures and dynamics of the R&D networks in robotics based on the co-patents between urban areas for the time periods under consideration. Starting with the global view on the robotics networks as a whole, we initially reflect on global network measures as described in Section 3, and also on the network visualizations. The latter employs Fruchterman-Rheingold visualization algorithms, i.e. placing central nodes in the center of the visualization, and placing nodes having many interaction and a same set of partners nearer to each other.

Before we turn to the urban area level, we want to take a brief look at the global robotics R&D networks at the level of countries, simply by aggregating links observed at the urban area level to the country level. Figure A2 in the Appendix provides the country-by-country network for the first and last time period. Most strikingly, the robotics network between countries become much denser, with many countries entering the network in the latest time period, or becoming much more central. While Germany, being the most central country in the first time period, the US and Japan mainly dominated the network from 2002-2006, other countries get in a much more central position in the latest time period such as the Netherlands, UK, France, Sweden, but also India, South Korea and China.

However, shifting attention to the networks observed at the level of urban areas enables a much more fine-grained picture, in particular in terms of the geographical dynamics. Table 2 presents the respective global SNA indicators, while Figure 2 visualizes the networks for the three time periods. Also, at the level of urban areas, results clearly indicate that the number of collaborations has increased significantly over the respective time period. The amount of edges almost doubled its value from 885 to 1,623 ties between the first and last period. Furthermore, actors are connected with 3.48 other actors on average in the most recent period. Looking at the time span, one can observe a substantial increase in the number of partners as the value of the average connectedness was at 1.90 in the first period.

Figure 2. Global area R&D collaboration network in robotics

Table 2. Global area SNA indicators in the R&D collaboration network

	2002-2006	2007-2011	2012-2016
# nodes	933	933	933
# edges	885	1,279	1,623
Degree centralisation	0.06	0.07	0.07
Average degree	1.90	2.74	3.48
Density	0.0020	0.0029	0.0037
Average path length	4.03	4.16	3.81
Clustering	0.23	0.27	0.23

Notes: Area abbreviations are provided in the Appendix (Table A2); Node color represents country of origin; Node size corresponds to the individual degree (Min. 15, Max. 90); Thickness of lines 0.2 (02-06;07-11) and 0.11(12-16); #denotes “number”

The visualizations (Figure 2) together with the top ten urban areas in terms of local SNA indicators (Table 3) help identifying underlying mechanism by looking at specific urban areas and their positioning in the network. It illustrates nicely the changing overall structure of the robotics R&D collaboration network on an area level over the observed time periods. It shows that the number of nodes (areas) participating in the collaboration network steadily increased from the first period (2002-2006) to the last period (2012-2016). The color and thickness of the lines suggests that the connections are much stronger within a country than between areas from different countries. For instance, Tokyo has enlarged collaborations with other areas from Japan (e.g. Osaka, Aichi) but only few connections to areas from other countries (and therefore also the relatively decreasing position at the country level, see Figure 4). Because connections are mainly concentrated within a country, color patterns are visible that point to some geographical logic in the network. Areas from Germany, China and Japan are visually grouped together as areas from these countries are mainly connected to one or few central hubs within the country that are further connected to international areas; a pattern that can also be related to the global pipelines versus local buzz considerations in the literature (see e.g. Bathelt, Malmberg, & Maskell, 2004). In the US there are more areas that show international connections which is why areas from the US are spread through the network structure. Moreover, it becomes obvious that urban areas from Sweden are moving closer to each other and also closer to urban areas from Germany. This indicates that the collaboration between areas from Sweden and Germany intensified while collaborations between areas from Sweden and the US weakened. The rise of Chinese urban areas can clearly be observed when comparing the visualizations of all three time periods. While Shanghai was the only urban area present in the first period, there are more than twenty areas from China illustrated in the network in the most recent time period. This is a significant and noteworthy change in the network structure as Chinese cities are now one of the dominant actors and no other country can show this intense development.

Looking at the top urban areas in terms of network centrality, it can be seen that Stuttgart and Tokyo are the two cities who show constantly the highest amount of connections, indicating that they hold a very influential position in the network. Urban areas who were able to increase their direct connections, such as Munich, Osaka, and Bavaria (Bayern rural), improved their integration into the network. In contrast, Detroit and Aichi lose their influential position slightly over time and are overruled by other areas. In fact, three areas from China – Shanghai, Guangzhou, and Beijing – show significant development in terms of direct connections. While their number of direct connections were 6 (Shanghai), 3 (Guangzhou) and 0 (Beijing) in the first period, they all have more than 45 direct connections with other actors in the last period and are hence much better integrated than other European urban areas, for instance (see Appendix Table A8). Figure 5 illustrates the reason for this increase: The significant surge of direct connections can be mainly attributed to a rise of other urban areas located in China and national connections to them.

Table 3. Top ten local area SNA indicators in the R&D collaboration network

2002-2006		2007-2011		2012-2016	
Area	Degree	Area	Degree	Area	Degree
Stuttgart	58	Stuttgart	68	Stuttgart	67
Tokyo	54	Tokyo	57	Tokyo	64
Detroit	51	Ba.-Wü.. rural	43	Munich	61
Munich	35	Munich	34	Shanghai	49
Aichi rural	33	Osaka	33	Guangzhou	49
Osaka	30	Anjo	31	Beijing	46
Ba.-Wü. rural	29	Detroit	30	Detroit	39
Anjo	27	Frankfurt a.M.	30	San Jose	38
Boston	23	Bayern rural	28	Osaka	38
NRW rural	21	Heidelberg	26	Bayern rural	36

2002-2006		2007-2011		2012-2016	
Area	Between.	Area	Between.	Area	Between.
Detroit	21313.32	Tokyo	23231.32	Detroit	29933.23
Stuttgart	13947.73	Detroit	15720.42	San Jose	19484.21
Tokyo	12949.14	Stuttgart	13770.02	Shanghai	19391.76
Paris	4045.02	Boston	10452.12	Paris	17987.63
Boston	3961.02	Paris	9506.84	Tokyo	17169.19
Lansing	3770.15	Anjo	7897.04	Munich	14970.95
Phoenix	3682.44	Seoul	7362.96	Stuttgart	13634.90
Santa Barbara	3496.79	Michigan rural	6056.30	Boston	10158.62
New York City	3186.50	Frankfurt a.M.	5877.25	London	10106.68
Illinois rural	3070.57	Chicago	5866.61	Guangzhou	9808.89

2002-2006		2007-2011		2012-2016	
Area	Eigenvector	Area	Eigenvector	Area	Eigenvector
Stuttgart	1.00	Stuttgart	1.00	Stuttgart	1.00
Munich	0.73	Ba.-Wü. rural.	0.75	Munich	0.86
Ba.-Wü. rural	0.62	Munich	0.64	Bayern rural	0.70
Tokyo	0.54	Frankfurt a.M.	0.61	Frankfurt a.M.	0.64
Detroit	0.53	Bayern rural	0.58	Ba.-Wü. rural.	0.63
Nuernberg	0.46	Nuernberg	0.53	Nuernberg	0.53
Pforzheim	0.44	Hannover	0.49	Karlsruhe	0.52
NRW rural	0.44	Augsburg	0.48	Hannover	0.52
Bayern rural	0.43	Heidelberg	0.46	Ingolstadt	0.51
Frankfurt a.M.	0.41	Karlsruhe	0.46	Augsburg	0.50

Most changes and movements can be interestingly observed for the betweenness centrality of the top ten actors. There have been major downward and upward developments of actors from the US in terms of global knowledge contribution. In the first period, Phoenix, Santa Barbara, and rural Illinois were able to influence and control the knowledge flow in the network significantly. However, all three areas show a downward trend and Santa Barbara even disappears completely from the collaboration network in the second and third period. Instead, the knowledge contribution role was shifted to the areas Boston, Detroit, and San Jose. While Detroit and Boston are constantly under the top ten betweenness indicators,

San Jose suddenly appears as the second influential knowledge contributor in the last period. Moving from the US to Germany, one can observe that Stuttgart is slightly less responsible for the global knowledge flow as the betweenness indicator decreases constantly over the time periods whereas Munich rises as an important actor in the collaboration network. Similar developments can be detected when taking a Japanese perspective: There is less global knowledge flow through Tokyo and more global knowledge flow through other Japanese areas such as Osaka, Anjo or Aichi. Moreover, the rise of Chinese areas (i.e. Shanghai and Guangzhou) can also be seen in the developments of their betweenness centralities.

Interestingly, German regions are extremely prominent in terms of eigenvector centrality. In fact, all areas listed in the top ten table – except from Tokyo and Detroit in the first period – are located in Germany. Furthermore, an extended list to the top fifty areas with the highest eigenvector centrality shows that the majority of areas come from Germany. Accordingly, German actors in robotics R&D collaboration networks are to much higher degree connected to other central countries, rather than to more peripheral ones. On the one hand, this shows the strong tradition of Germany in the robotics landscape, but, on the other hand, it is less connected with emerging new players not central in the network yet, but probably in the future.

In sum, the analysis shows the quite dynamic character of the global robotics R&D collaboration, with changing roles in the network of different places on earth, both within as well as between countries. The overall trend of rising R&D activities and collaborations is striking, as is the importance of spatial shifts driven by technological evolution, but also other intervening factors, e.g. strong public R&D funding for the sector in specific places. While the systematic identification of drivers and more detailed explanations of these observed patterns is out of scope of this study, it provides the basis for future research in this direction by systematically characterizing this changing landscape at a global, and at the same time very detailed geographical level.

6 Discussion and concluding remarks

In recent years, the robotics market has been growing significantly – mainly in manufacturing industries such in automotive, electronics or pharma, but increasingly also in service industries – and is expected to grow further in the future. Given its high research intensity in combination with the substantial growth and transformative potential for the economy and the society, robotics is widely considered as breakthrough innovation, both in the scientific realm as well as by policy makers around the world. In fact, the implementation of different kinds of robots in industrial production processes and distribution cycles substantially influences the socio-economic development of firms in terms of productivity, efficiency, competition, and labour, but also of the society in terms of increased usages of robots in the service and social sector, e.g. health. Clearly, robots already are and will be even more a key instrument for socio-economic activities and the work environment in the coming years.

As a highly research- and capital-intensive segment, the robotic landscape requires a high level of expertise and knowledge as well as sufficient resources. Therefore, it can be assumed that R&D collaborations also become increasingly important in the robotics segment, based on insights from innovation studies telling us that the successful generation of new knowledge as a basis for innovation is increasingly conducted within a complex web of interacting researching actors (firms, universities, research organisations, intermediaries, agencies, etc.). Moreover, given the high investment of public authorities, national governments and supra-national organisations in robotics R&D, the global robotics R&D landscape is assumed to change dynamically, both in terms of its geographical distribution and thematic orientation.

However, so far, we find only scarce empirical insights into the geography of global R&D robotics and its dynamics – both in terms of the identification of R&D hot spots and how robotics collaboration networks develop over time. Against this background, the aim of this study was to identify and characterise the changing R&D landscape in robotics, for the first time globally and through very detailed geographical lenses of global urban areas. Emphasis has been shifted to trace global R&D hotspots and characterise geographical specialisation patterns in robotics worldwide, and to identify and illustrate dynamics of underlying global robotics R&D collaboration networks, also at the level of global urban areas. We use – following previous literature – patents as an indicator for commercially oriented R&D activities, and co-patents as an indicator for inventive collaborative activities. In our empirical approach, we have mobilized a large sample dataset comprising more than 42,000 patents applied for from 2002-2016, shifting attention to three time periods for tracing dynamics (2002-2006, 2007-2011 and 2012-2016). We identify R&D hotspots and the geography of specialisation in robotics through the Revealed Technological Advantage (RTA) index, while we employ a Social Network Analysis (SNA) perspective to trace robotics R&D collaboration networks based on the identified co-patents. In particular, the geocoding of the innovative patent dataset at the level of urban areas has offered completely new spatial-analytical possibilities, both for the identification of global hot spots and global network structures at a much more detailed level of spatial granularity.

The empirical analysis based on this novel dataset indeed has provided substantial new insights on the global geography of the robotics R&D landscape. *First*, we identify most prominent urban hot spots in terms of specializing in robotics R&D; the most specialized urban areas are located in Germany, the US, Japan, but also Sweden. Chinese urban areas, though not belonging to the top hot spots yet, have most ascenders, many urban areas climbing up the specialization ranking substantially over the observed time periods. *Second*, we find that – in accordance with theoretical considerations – global robotics R&D has grown immense both in total patenting, but also in terms of R&D collaboration activities between urban areas. The global networks density and average number of collaboration partners has nearly duplicated between the periods 2002-2006 and 2012-2016. *Third*, the growth is by far not equally distributed in geographical space, but is characterized by significant spatial shifts, both in terms of cities declining or climbing up the specialization ranking, but even more in terms of the spatial network structure. In the

latter context, most strikingly a high number of Chinese urban areas are entering the network, with three cities (Beijing, Shanghai and Guangzhou) now belonging to globally most central urban areas in robotics R&D. These three areas act as important knowledge ‘gatekeepers’ of the Chinese cities, distributing knowledge into the Chinese system since other cities are much more nationally oriented. Next to these Chinese cities, the urban area network is mainly dominated by urban areas located in Germany (e.g. Stuttgart, Munich), the US (e.g. Detroit, San Jose) and Japan (e.g. Tokyo, Osaka). *Fourth*, the observed spatial shifts can be to a substantial degree attributed to changing thematic priorities in robotics R&D. While we find the classical automotive oriented cities exclusively on top in the earliest period, other fields of application, such as household, agriculture and forestry, are at stake under the most growing cities in terms of specialization but also network centrality (Stockholm and Aichi). *Fifth*, we interestingly find a stronger role of public research organizations in Asian than in other countries active in robotics R&D. This could be related to the fact that public R&D funding of robotics played a substantial role in those countries, in particular China. *Sixth*, intra-national shifts are remarkable and made visible by the analysis; for instance, in the US, some urban areas have increased their network centrality remarkably (e.g. San Jose), while others lose their position (e.g. Santa Barbara).

From a policy perspective, the study produces a number of implications, but also raises question marks that should be addressed in future research endeavors. Public R&D funding instruments obviously played a strong role for the catching-up process of Asian countries, in particular China. What is somewhat surprising is that this catching-up is even more pronounced in the changing network structure, where Asian cities tend to get in very central position, and therefore to a larger degree get a broader view on the knowledge being circulated. Against this background, some ideas for future research come into mind. In the policy context, for instance, it would be urgently needed to investigate drivers of the observed patterns from an explanatory, e.g. modelling, perspective. This tackles both drivers of specialization patterns (why do some urban areas become more specialized places?), and the networks dynamics (what determines collaboration intensity between two urban areas, and drives specific urban areas to reach a more central network position?). Moreover, changing thematic orientations and applications fields, e.g. by looking at specializations and networks of specific subdomains within robotics, are of great interest for follow-up research.

Acknowledgements

This was supported by RISIS2 (Research Infrastructure for and Innovation Policy Studies 2), funded by the European Union’s Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme under the grant number n°824091”.

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Appendix A: Data extraction and preparation

Table A1. Brief overview of the selected CPC classes

CPC	Definition 3-Digit	Definition on most detailed level
B25J 9/16	Manipulators; chambers provided with manipulation devices	Programme controls
B25J 9/20		Fluidic
B25J 9/0003		Home robots, i.e. small robots for domestic use
B25J 11/0005		Manipulators having means for high-level communication with users, e.g. speech generator, face recognition means
B25J 11/0015		Face robots, animated artificial faces for imitating human expressions
B60W 30	Conjoint control of vehicle sub-units of different type or different function; control systems specially adapted for hybrid vehicles; road vehicle drive control systems for purposes not related to the control of a particular sub-unit	Purposes of road vehicle drive control systems not related to the control of a particular sub-unit, e.g. of systems using conjoint control of vehicle sub-units
B60W 20/30		Control strategies involving selection of transmission gear ratio
Y10S 901	Technical subjects covered by former USPC* cross-reference art collections [XRACS] and digests	Robots
G05D 1/0088	Systems for controlling or regulating non-electric variables	characterized by the autonomous decision-making process, e.g. artificial intelligence, predefined behaviours
G05D 1/02		Control of position or course in two dimensions
G05D 1/03		using near-field transmission systems, e.g. inductive-loop type
G05D 2201/0207		Unmanned vehicle for inspecting or visiting an area
G05D 2201/0212		Driverless passenger transport vehicle

Notes: More detailed definitions and classifications of the (sub)classes can be found on [Cooperative Patent Classification - Table](#) (European Patent Office & United States and Trademark Office, 2021). *USPC = [United States Patent Classification](#)

Figure A1. Global country R&D collaboration network in robotics

2002 – 2006

2012 – 2016

Table A2. RTA analysis of areas with total patent count greater than 2,000

Area	Patents robotics 2012-2016	Total patents 2012-2016	RTA 2012-2016
Ann Arbor	99.6038	2606.1905	20.0875
Stockholm	190.7605	5262.1416	19.0538
Detroit	325.539	9739.4012	17.5682
Aichi - rural	399.1836	14594.7241	14.3758
Kitakyushu	88.4004	3480.8105	13.3484
Stuttgart	384.842	15364.3453	13.1651
Karlsruhe	49.3509	2290.7401	11.3233
Goeteborg	75.8621	3533.6226	11.2839
Munich	229.877	11622.7685	10.3954
Frankfurt am Main	68.307	4066.8358	8.8280
Kofu	37.2826	2551.9445	7.6787
Michigan - rural	28.9795	2874.0367	5.2997
Bayern - rural	47.3114	4912.1480	5.0623
Baden-Württemberg - rural	47.6616	5334.5862	4.6959
Regensburg	26.0096	3021.1313	4.5250
Anjo	170.3926	23285.8546	3.8460
Pittsburgh	17.8494	2638.7016	3.5554
Berlin	29.7704	4476.9876	3.4951
Changwon	17.7179	2674.7968	3.4816
Paris	245.2848	37101.3071	3.4749
Fukuoka	31.5336	4860.1611	3.4102
Nuernberg	40.4428	6611.1127	3.2153
Seattle	82.3235	13620.9592	3.1767
Dresden	12.2429	2141.6889	3.0046
Aachen	19.3106	3432.7744	2.9567
Nagano - rural	82.9888	15094.8380	2.8897
Koeln	12.8773	2428.8311	2.7867
Toulouse	20.9825	4251.2202	2.5942
Heidelberg	9.4831	2259.0396	2.2064
Nordrhein-Westfalen - rural	16.0942	3889.4158	2.1749
Essen	16.3332	4071.0165	2.1087
Seoul	387.5369	97910.1571	2.0804
Numazu	18.4359	4661.1369	2.0789
Mito	22.0044	5903.9678	1.9589
San Francisco	76.87	22050.2013	1.8323
San Jose	131.719	38511.2902	1.7977
Hamburg	11.8166	3704.9300	1.6764
South Chungcheong - rural	12.8802	4043.1245	1.6744
Malmoe	6.6667	2095.9729	1.6718
Mannheim	10.4022	3326.7849	1.6434
Baltimore	6.8333	2232.8480	1.6085
Cleveland	8.3664	2768.7451	1.5882
Los Angeles	39.3828	13746.6324	1.5058
Boston	54.177	19343.2694	1.4721

Gyeonggi - rural	6.5666	2385.3474	1.4469
Chicago	28.083	10697.7723	1.3798
Toronto	12.6413	4943.5718	1.3440
Yamaguchi - rural	18.6959	7946.4192	1.2366
Hamamatsu	46.9213	20090.8018	1.2275
Raleigh	9.8664	4305.2650	1.2045
Daegu	12.4333	5452.0179	1.1986
North Gyeongsang - rural	4.5334	2019.1473	1.1801
Daejeon	34.3407	15695.0946	1.1500
Mission Viejo	4.3999	2059.5769	1.1228
Grenoble	6.6499	3238.4945	1.0793
San Diego	33.3499	16563.4541	1.0583
Ulsan	5.2856	2718.3200	1.0220
Zurich	7.2083	3709.4328	1.0214
Singapore	11.1662	5933.4753	0.9891
Sendai	8.316	4423.3725	0.9881
Tel Aviv	9.5829	5387.6242	0.9349
Lyon	4.7331	2696.4584	0.9226
Helsinki	6.5	3807.5031	0.8973
Busan	4.861	2848.1115	0.8971
Duesseldorf	4.35	2590.9669	0.8824
London	14.5452	8880.4578	0.8609
Albany	6.1836	3782.6148	0.8592
Gwangju	5.8596	3631.0057	0.8482
Sapporo	4.4997	2801.3830	0.8442
Ontario - rural	5.125	3191.3375	0.8441
South Gyeongsang - rural	6.3953	3991.3479	0.8422
Denver	4.6666	2918.1252	0.8405
St Louis	3.575	2357.5373	0.7970
Austin	9.7083	6510.5401	0.7838
Ibaraki - rural	26.8384	19138.7834	0.7371
Utsunomiya	5.9583	4806.6155	0.6515
Hokkaidō - rural	6.2046	5233.5838	0.6231
Miami	3.3334	2858.1512	0.6130
Taipei	32.6736	28195.9127	0.6091
Copenhagen	3.3498	3208.5792	0.5487
Shizuoka - rural	12.9407	12900.2024	0.5272
Toyohashi	2.3667	2459.5703	0.5058
Chengdu	11.8917	12366.6973	0.5054
Washington DC	4.712	4924.8535	0.5029
Jiaying	2.2025	2306.0182	0.5020
Concord	3.7736	3980.5257	0.4983
Kaohsiung	11.2617	12018.4671	0.4925
Minneapolis	8.2997	8912.4842	0.4895
Maebashi	3.6666	4242.1182	0.4543
Atlanta	4.6668	5400.6588	0.4542
Zhenjiang	2.2	2677.9124	0.4318
Phoenix	3.4333	4204.2168	0.4292

Dallas	5.1168	6459.8771	0.4163
Tokyo	552.7322	727655.5067	0.3992
Portland	4.3332	6126.6939	0.3717
Rochester	2.7499	3948.5149	0.3660
Nagano	1.6999	2497.5236	0.3577
Tochigi - rural	2.65	4151.4386	0.3355
Zhejiang - rural	1.5	2396.1296	0.3290
Eindhoven	3.7916	6239.5121	0.3194
Hiroshima	2.95	4914.7498	0.3155
Hartford	2.0595	3493.8062	0.3098
Shanghai	65.9938	112058.7055	0.3095
Osaka	155.268	264757.9038	0.3082
Toyama	2	3543.1130	0.2967
Niigata - rural	1.3333	2433.7469	0.2879
Matsuyama	2.6666	5068.3380	0.2765
Basel	2.3333	4446.9228	0.2758
Himeji	1.5833	3025.9206	0.2750
Milan	1.3334	2673.9432	0.2621
Zhuzhou	1.1429	2436.9521	0.2465
Delhi	1	2156.5920	0.2437
Nagoya	40.4394	87802.9153	0.2421
Changsha	3.0001	6519.8573	0.2419
Indianapolis	1.1166	2583.7355	0.2271
Cincinnati	1.3	3120.2653	0.2190
Houston	4.075	9858.3069	0.2173
Chongqing	2	4906.5910	0.2142
Orlando	0.9999	2460.0726	0.2136
Qingdao	6.1028	15332.5896	0.2092
Changchun	1.475	3879.1760	0.1999
Gangwon	1.0834	2873.4009	0.1982
Jiangxi - rural	3.1039	8301.0692	0.1965
Montreal	0.9583	2676.7851	0.1882
Datong	0.8191	2440.7227	0.1764
Guangzhou	92.6418	280784.8325	0.1734
Philadelphia	2.2	6793.5031	0.1702
New York City	12.6164	39354.0552	0.1685
Shenyang	1.4585	4731.5508	0.1620
Guangxi - rural	1.1	3653.8960	0.1582
New York - rural	1.4833	5024.4832	0.1552
Wuhan	4.2833	15104.5888	0.1490
Beijing	46.1814	190472.4488	0.1274
Hong Kong	0.9916	4143.0957	0.1258
Ningbo	0.9	3893.5575	0.1215
Yokkaichi	1.1191	5122.7893	0.1148
Niigata	0.6222	2865.3574	0.1141
Hefei	0.75	3461.5485	0.1139
Jiangsu - rural	2.2193	10411.0572	0.1120
Bengaluru	1.35	6501.0012	0.1091

Nanjing	3.2859	16427.0728	0.1051
Tianjin	2.2946	12667.9345	0.0952
Hangzhou	2.5262	14491.0786	0.0916
Dalian	0.604	3469.1682	0.0915
Nantong	1.05	6488.0747	0.0851
Sichuan - rural	0.3429	2158.4521	0.0835
Fujian - rural	1.575	10086.0397	0.0821
Fuzhou	0.3333	2361.5136	0.0742
Hubei - rural	0.4167	2989.2101	0.0733
Weifang	0.25	2093.6808	0.0628
Sydney	0.3333	2802.0638	0.0625
Liaoning - rural	0.2679	2266.3547	0.0621
Vancouver	0.25	2259.7940	0.0581
Shantou	0.3052	2957.0524	0.0542
Jilin	0.25	2424.5140	0.0542
Jinan	0.625	6255.1375	0.0525
Zhuhai	0.5929	6122.1204	0.0509
Guangdong - rural	0.4	4158.3924	0.0506
Hebei - rural	0.2917	3383.2289	0.0453
Moscow	0.45	6465.4635	0.0366

Table A3. Top three actors in top ten RTA areas

Area	Patent applicant
Ann Arbor	Ford Global Technologies, LLC GM Global Technology Operations LLC Toyota Motor Engineering & Manufacturing North America, Inc
Stockholm	Aktiebolaget Electrolux Husqvarna AB Scania CV AB
Detroit	Ford Global Technologies, LLC GM Global Technology Operations LLC Nissan North America, Inc.
Aichi - rural	AISIN AW CO LTD Toyota Jidosha Kabushiki Kaisha TOYOTA MOTOR CORP
Kitakyushu	Kabushiki Kaisha Yaskawa Denki National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology YASKAWA ELECTRIC CORP
Stuttgart	DAIMLER AG Robert Bosch GmbH Valeo Schalter und Sensoren GmbH
Karlsruhe	DAIMLER AG Robert Bosch GmbH SEW-EURODRIVE GMBH & CO KG
Goeteborg	Volvo Car Corporation VOLVO TRUCK CORPORATION
Munich	Bayerische Motoren Werke Aktiengesellschaft Kuka Roboter GmbH MAN Truck & Bus AG
Frankfurt am Main	Continental Teves AG & Co. OHG GM GLOBAL TECHNOLOGY OPERATIONS LLC Honda Research Institute Europe GmbH